

EBFMC25-OP-39 · Study on the Validity and Reliability of the Spiritual Intelligence Scale in Physicians

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Historically, many studies have been conducted on Physical Quotient (PQ) and Intelligence Quotient (IQ) and in recent years, the concepts of Emotional Quotient (EQ) and Spiritual Quotient (SQ) have also come to the fore and research on the importance of different intelligence dimensions in terms of a person's performance in both social and professional areas is increasing day by day. The aim of this study is to examine the validity and reliability of the Spiritual Intelligence Scale, developed by Kumar and Mehta (Kumar & Mehta, 2011) and adapted to Turkish by Erduran and Ekşi, and its validity and reliability examined in adolescents (Erduran & Tekin, 2019).

Materials and Methods: This study, which is a methodological research; In February – June 2023, the questionnaire was sent to the registered phone numbers of the physicians with the Google questionnaire file and it was carried out with 301 volunteer physicians. In the first part of the questionnaire, questions containing sociodemographic information were included. Statistical data analysis was performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics 26.0 package program (IBM Corp., Armonk, New York, USA). Construct validity, criterion-related validity, internal consistency reliability, two-half test reliability (divided into two halves) and item analysis methods were used. Explanatory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) were performed on the data obtained for construct validity (Tabachnick BG, 2013).

Results: The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the Spiritual Intelligence Scale was calculated as 0.807. The Barlett sphericity test of the scale was found to be 1253.557 ($p < 0.001$), and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin coefficient (KMO) was 0.806, and it was decided that our data were suitable for EFA. As a result of the factor analysis, it was determined that the items were gathered under 4 factors with Eigenvalues greater than 1 and 4 factors explained 47.563% of the cumulative variance. The result of the confirmatory factor analysis was calculated as $\chi^2/df = 2.086$, $p = < 0.001$.

Conclusion: Spiritual intelligence scale was found to be a reliable and valid scale that can be used by physicians ($\alpha = 0.807$).

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Spiritual intelligence, validity, reliability, spiritual care, spirituality

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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